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**TEACHERS PREFERENCES TOWARDS INNOVATIVE
PEDAGOGY USING ICT IN VARANASI**

Ayush Kumar

Assistant Professor, Institute of Management Studies, Mahatma
Gandhi Kashi Vidyapith (A U.P. State University) Varanasi, India
Email : bliss.ayush31@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The integration of information and communication technologies can help revitalize teachers and students. This can be helpful in improving and developing the quality of education by providing curricular support in difficult subject areas. To achieve these objectives, teachers need to be involved in collaborative projects and development of intervention change strategies, which would include teaching partnerships with ICT as a tool. In this paper preferences of various schools/ UG & PG teachers are analyzed and various factors are carefully examined, that affect their preference towards the use of various ICT tools as effective teaching- learning methodology. The first hand data is collected through questionnaire from colleges/ school teachers to draw the inference and considered their valuable suggestions that they mentioned in questionnaire.

Keywords: Teaching; Information Technology; Learning; Innovative Teaching; Pedagogy; Communication Technology

INTRODUCTION

Pedagogy is the term generally refers to strategies of instruction, or a style of instruction to the Lerner for the sake of imparting/ delivering content to them. The innovative teaching may be defined as all those newer practices that enhance the pedagogy of teaching and made it efficient for learners to grasp the knowledge in very imperative way. The term e-mode of teaching is ambiguous to all those outside the e-teaching industry, and even within its diverse disciplines it has different meanings to different people. For instance, in companies it often refers to the strategies that uses the company network to deliver training courses to employees and lately in most Universities, ICT's e- mode of teaching is used to attend a course or program of study where the students rarely or never meet face-to-face, nor access on-campus educational facilities, because they study online whereas in case of class room based teaching various ICT tools can be used according to comfort zone of instructor like use of projector, electronic content/ e-books, video streaming, podcast, video conferencing, VSAT, cloud computing, email, discussion boards, blogs, wikis, virtual class room etc. are various tools used by mentor in class room as well as in non class room based teaching. In Varanasi, most of educational institutions and college are lacking behind in context of ICT infrastructure whereas some colleges of professional courses have developed a well equipped class rooms with innovative techniques. Some public schools have tied up with Educom to impart knowledge in a very attractive and alive way.

Barriers to Growth of ICT Mode of Teaching

Source: Bingimlas (2009)

No doubt there are various barriers to the innovative teaching methodology some are related with the teachers' side and some are with college side but ultimately growth is barred. Colleges lack willpower to adopt new methodology either due to financial constraints, training or lack of technical support which implement the desired technology. At a same time teachers/trainers as a human nature opposes the change. They sometime lack commitment and confidence in playing with new technology and tries to remain in saturated state.

Skills May Required For Success of ICT Pedagogy

- Basic Computer operation
- File Management and searching
- Data manipulation and management
- Online community building
- Discussion forum

LITERATURE REVIEW

According to UNESCO (2002) information and communication technology may be considered as the integration of information technology with communication technology. There are various types of ICT instruments available which are very relevant to education, such as interactive radio counseling, audio conferencing, television lessons, teleconferencing, email, radio broadcasts, interactive voice response system, CD ROMs and audiocassettes etc. have been used in education for teaching purposes (Sanyal, 2001; Sharma, 2003; Bhattacharya and Sharma, 2007).

According to a United Nations report (1999) ICTs cover Internet service provision, telecommunications equipment and services, information technology equipment and services, media and broadcasting, libraries and documentation centers, commercial information providers, network-based information services, and other related information and communication activities. If attitude of peoples and their relation is discussed the Rogers five features of technology can't be ignore, according to Rogers (1995) the major factors affecting peoples mind is actually related with features of the technology itself. He points out five basic features of technology that is having effect over its acceptance and adoption: (i) relative advantage (ii) compatibility (iii) complexity (iv) observability and (v) trialability. So, a technology will only flourish if potential adopters think that the present innovation has an advantage over previous innovations. Zhao and Cziko (2001) talked about three

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conditions which are necessary for teachers to implement ICT into their classrooms that teachers should have strong believe in the effectiveness of technology, they should also believe that the use of technology will not cause any disturbances, and finally teachers should believe that they have control over technology. Harris (2002) conducted case studies in three primary and three secondary schools, whose focus area was various innovative pedagogical practices involving ICT. He concludes that the benefits of ICT will be achieved only when confident and motivated teachers are willing to explore new opportunities for changing their classroom practices by using ICT.

OBJECTIVES

This research aims to the following objective, they are as follows:-

1. To know the techno- savvy behaviour among teachers of Varanasi.
2. To know the view of teachers towards traditional and online teaching.
3. To perform demographical analysis of teachers towards e – teaching.
4. To know the effect of teacher’s qualification level on their preference to e – teaching.
5. To know the preference and awareness of teachers towards (mobile) m- teaching.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research is a human activity based on intellectual investigation and is aimed at discovering, interpreting and revising human knowledge on different aspect of the world. The aim of research is reached by the help of inference drawn through primary data with sample size of 100. Universe of study is Varanasi and sampling unit is teachers of different school, graduate and post graduate colleges. Questionnaires technique is used to collect primary data.

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Table 1. No of Male and Female Respondents

Gender	No of respondent
Male	78%
Female	22%

There was 78 % male and 22% female Respondent was interacted during survey Process.

Table 2. Age group of teachers

Age group	No of teachers
20 - 30	16%
30 - 40	44%
40 - 50	24%
50 - 60	14%
60 - 70	2%

Interpretation

- 16% teacher belongs to the age group of 20-30.
- 44% teacher belongs to the age group of 30-40.
- 24% teacher belongs to the age group of 40-50.
- 14% teacher belongs to the age group of 50-60.
- 2% teacher belongs to the age group of 60-70.

Table 3. Highest Qualification of Teacher

Qualification	No. Of teachers
Undergraduate	20%
Post graduate	37%
M. Phil	3%
Ph.D/D.Phil	40%

Interpretation

- 20% teachers are having undergraduate technical qualification.
- 37% teachers are having technical & non technical post graduate qualification.
- 3% teachers are M.Phil.
- 40% teachers are awarded Ph.D/D.Phil as highest qualification.

Table 4. School/ College's profile

Profile	No of teachers
Private	52%
Aided	15%
Government	33%

Interpretation

- 52% teachers are from private institution.
- 33% teachers are from government institution.
- 15% teachers are from aided institution.

Table 5. Your stream of teaching

Stream	No. Of teachers
Science	23%
Arts	46%
Commerce	5%
Management	26%

Interpretation

- 23% teachers are teaching with science stream.
- 46% teachers are teaching with arts stream.
- 5% teachers are teaching with commerce stream.
- 26% teachers are teaching with management stream.

Table 6. Your frequency of using internet and communication services

Mode	Frequency
Never used	16%
Occasionally	29%
Frequent	55%

Interpretation

- 16% teachers have never used internet and communication services.
- 29% teachers use internet and communication services occasionally.

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- 55% teachers are frequent with internet and communication services.

Table 7. Which is effective and advantageous in your view?

Method	No. of views
Traditional teaching	57%
ICT mode of teaching	15%
Both	28%

Interpretation

- 57% teachers of Varanasi are in favour that, traditional teaching is effective and advantageous.
- 15% teachers of Varanasi think ICT mode of teaching is fruitful.
- 28% teachers appreciated both methods as effective & advantageous.

Table 8. If you have chance for ICT mode of teaching, will you prefer it?

Mode	Preference
Yes	77%
No	23%

Interpretation

- On chance, 77% teachers of Varanasi will prefer ICT mode of teaching.
- 23% teachers of Varanasi will refuse to opt for this mode.

Table 9. What is your current teaching method?

Methods	Current Mode
Traditional	57%
Online	2%
Mix of both	41%

Interpretation

- 57% teachers of Varanasi are teaching traditionally.
- 2% teachers of Varanasi are using online method for teaching.
- 41% teachers of Varanasi use both methods simultaneously.

Table 10. Mobile learning got cheapest and easiest way of learning. Do you support this statement?

Mode	Views
Yes	48%
No	52%

Interpretation

- 48% teachers of Varanasi supports that, m- learning is cheapest and easiest way of learning.
- 52% teachers of Varanasi think that, it is expensive and difficult

Table 11. What is your preference if you have chance for m- teaching in future?

Mode	Preference
Will use	42%
Will reject	22%
Just try	36%

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- 42% teachers will utilize the chance of m- teaching in future.
- 22% teachers will reject the above chance.
- 36% teachers are ready to try this new concept

FINDINGS

- A huge community of respondent will prefer ICT pedagogy, if they are given chance for it.
- Most of the respondent is from male community (78%) and they are frequent with internet & communication services.
- Most of the respondent are belongs to the age group of 30-40 and their preference towards ICT pedagogy is remarkable.
- The no. of respondent having Ph.D/D.Phil or post graduate qualification is approximately same but P.G. respondents are more responsive towards ICT & mobile teaching methods.
- Respondents having professional/technical qualification are more techno savvy and inclined towards online teaching tools.
- The numbers of private school/colleges are more than the government & aided in Varanasi and the respondents from private school/college are more frequent and preferential towards innovative teaching tools and communication services.
- Management as well as science stream respondent mostly uses ICT pedagogical tools in comparison to arts and commerce.
- Respondent from government school/college are aware about the internet communication tools and partially/ rarely prefer the online teaching methods.
- On account of effectiveness, the most preferred teaching method is traditional (57%) where as a small community (28%) of respondent say both methods are effective & advantageous simultaneously.
- The current teaching method of most of the respondents are traditional where as a large community of respondents uses both methods according to their convenience.
- More than half of the respondent refused that m- teaching is cheapest and easiest way of learning.
- Most of the respondent will utilize the offer of m- teaching, where as some just try to become familiar with this new concept of teaching.

SUGGESTIONS

- ICT pedagogy is an innovative technique in the educational institution, but it would be applicable unless and until our educational institutions are well equipped with required infrastructure and trained manpower.
- There must be combination of traditional and ICT pedagogy, as traditional teaching means face to face interaction, so it is also required at least once in a week.
- There should not be prompt change in the teaching pedagogy but slowly it should be upgraded.
- ICT mode of teaching should be appreciated to provide stress free study environment for student as well as teachers also.

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- ICT mode of teaching is an effective and convenience mode for spreading the education across the world but one can't questions the significance and effectiveness of traditional teaching methodology.
- ICT mode of teaching will be very influential to the student especially for those who belong to rural/ remote areas.
- Online teaching of course plays a vital role in dissemination of information but traditional teaching include more lively discussion then online and involves an emotional touch.

CONCLUSIONS

- Teachers of Varanasi are frequent towards internet communication technology.
- ICT pedagogy lack social interaction, which leads to lack the Behavioral development of the students.
- Traditional teaching is still mostly preferred.
- Online teaching is nice way of teaching but it should be combined with traditional teaching for better result.
- Teachers belonging to age group of 30-40 are more preferential towards innovative teaching.
- Male teachers have huge preference to online teaching in comparison to female teachers.
- Teachers having post graduate degree as highest qualification are largely inclined to prefer ICT pedagogy and m- teaching.
- m- Teaching is costly, but it is accepted by the huge community of teachers.

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